

RF COMMUNICATION DATA MODEL FOR SATELLITE NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the database structure of an RF taxonomy modeling tool being developed on a Missile Defense Agency (MDA), Phase II, Small Business Innovative Research (SBIR) augmentation contract. The tool is called the Communications System Taxonomy (CommTax) toolkit. The data model underlying the CommTax toolkit will be available to other users as a framework for the transfer of data to other system design tools. With the augmentation authorization, CommTax will include interoperability with Analytical Graphics, Inc. (AGI) Satellite Toolkit (STK), satellite modeling tool as well as the original task of interoperating with Scalable Network Technology's (SNT) QualNet network modeling tool. Interoperability with STK will enable a better visualization of a scenario that is set-up and run with CommTax. The QualNet interoperability enables CommTax to determine whether a scenario model is capable of passing enough data fast enough over the various IP and bit-stream, wired and wireless MDA networks to support a successful running of a scenario even if other data could cause congestion on the networks.

The purpose of CommTax is to enable the communication engineer to model communications among multiple disparate nodes in the BMDS using Internet Protocol (IP) compliant networks for interconnection. The database framework and data interoperability objectives of the CommTax toolkit, are described in this paper

INTRODUCTION

Communication and network system architects, engineers, and integrators need access to simple, intuitive tools for performing system trades and analyses of complex, layered, system of systems architectures. A Missile Defense Agency (MDA) Phase II Small Business Innovation Research (SBIR) project, Communications System Taxonomy (CommTax) is building a capability for communication planners, system engineers, and radio frequency (RF) designers to assemble commercial off the shelf (COTS) components or legacy government off the shelf (GOTS) RF and network systems into a complex end-to-end (E2E) communication system model. The objectives, usage scenarios, and typical user interfaces of the CommTax toolkit has been described in *A Modeling Tool for Joining RF Communications with IP Networks*, a paper presented at MILCOM 2008 [1].

This paper describes the data interoperability objectives, database, and data model details powering the CommTax tool. It also covers the migration path to parallel Modeling and Simulation initiatives.

Today's system of systems (SoS) is characterized by a myriad of options that must all be considered before committing a proposed communication system design to hardware and eventual operational implementation. This complex trade space presents interesting problems for designers; since E2E communications systems are often so complex that system designers have difficulty keeping track of the trades, constraints, interface requirements, and interdependencies among components [2]. Components could be COTS, GOTS, or those procured in parallel by other agencies. Excellent COTS network design tools, such as QualNet and OPNET, exist for planning and designing networks. These tools, which are centered on utilizing networking technologies, also include radio communication models, but not to the detail needed to actually plan and design them. These network-modeling tools generally require well-trained network design specialists to operate, and often require interaction with other specialists, such as communication engineers, to get their detailed inputs as piecemeal results obtained with manual hand-tuning. Errors and miss-communication are hard to avoid. Large SoS interactions are hard to model, simulate, analyze, and validate. Furthermore, those same network tools are usually not available to the radio communication implementers.

Object oriented and model based development tools are emerging in design environments enabling designers to assemble software-described 'components' into system models for emulation and test. Equivalent combinations of modeling and simulation capabilities are in development by DOD Modeling and Simulation communities [3]. CommTax enables the communication system designers to 'assemble' the software-described communication components into the chains of RF transmit and receive equipment used in the E2E design of space/ground networks.

As more communication systems are incorporated into network centric architecture, the current patchwork of ad-hoc and proprietary communication tools becomes unwieldy for meeting the modeling, analysis, development, and validation needs of network centric communication architecture spanning a federation of independent communication systems that have to work as a SoS to meet stringent MDA mission requirements. CommTax is designed using modular building blocks that can be extended to provide interfaces to other popular modeling tools.

A typical CommTax usage scenario, via MDA BMDS Engagement Sequence Groups (ESGs) is presented in the MILCOM 2008 paper and summarized below after a short review of the CommTax toolkit.[1]

COMMTAX SUMMARY

CommTax simplifies the integration of RF components into network models, thus enabling RF engineers to collaborate with network engineers on developing the complex communications needed in all MDA and Global Information Grid (GIG) areas. CommTax provides simple graphical user interfaces (GUIs) to manage the complexity of MDA communications systems, networks, and mission visualizations. Real hardware characteristics are entered into a database via the CommTax GUI. CommTax then uses that information in the communication models that are also entered via the GUI.

CommTax features physical views, logical scenario views, and unified summary views of interdependencies among components, interfaces, and protocols in the information system being studied. The most important elements of the CommTax Toolkit are its ability to present RF and network layer dependencies in one unified model and to maintain detailed, static and dynamic instances of that model in a comprehensive database that can also be transformed and integrated with the databases of other modeling tools. The CommTax model, which is used to visualize the use of RF systems in Internet Protocol (IP) networks, recognizes the protocols and technologies used in those networks and conforms to the seven-layer Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) model [4].

The CommTax Toolkit offers system designers, integrators, and operators a common model to describe the system on any scale ranging from subsystems including routers, modems, and amplifiers, to large-scale SoS implementations encompassing regional-, national- or global-scale operations. For the MDA application, CommTax can be applied to ground-to/from-missile, sensor-to-operations, and E2E data path designs and descriptions.

A typical CommTax model consists of fixed-site and mobile nodes connected or arranged in a network. Each node is represented as an object with parameter and variable attributes that describe it and its location or path of motion. Nodes are generally self-contained facilities or vehicles that are separated geographically and are either mobile (ships, interceptors, trucks, aircraft, satellites, etc.) or fixed-site (operations centers, satellite ground stations, fixed-site radars, etc.). Several node types are typically capable of transmitting/receiving RF signals and modulating/demodulating digital information to/from the RF respectively. Other node types include control centers and other non-RF, network-compliant, ground based operation locations. Nodes are connected together in a network either over IP ground lines or through the air by

surface and satellite RF links. Communication and network components, such as receivers, transmitters, frequency converters, modulators, coders, encryption devices, routers, etc., are treated within a node as objects that each have their own attributes that may be modeled within CommTax. Actual component attributes and values can be entered into the model as well as idealized values for future components. The CommTax Toolkit contains a library of commonly referenced components, such as IP routers, satellite modems, frequency converters, and amplifiers.

CommTax is used to model the interfaces between components in the model. This enables the designer to include the physical attributes of connectors, wiring, and free space characteristics of the wireless links into the network model. Since all of the system's elements are defined by active software models, system designers are able to change key parameters, such as modulation scheme, channel frequency, coding schemes, data rates, interface characteristics, and etc., and see the effects those changes have on other elements in the model and overall system performance.

CommTax models are built in modular blocks to simplify development, to enable integration with existing COTS products, and to provide a solid framework for adding future product features. The development environment for CommTax is the Microsoft .NET framework and Visual Studio .NET 2005. The ESRI Company's ArcGIS 9.2 is used for scenario mapping. The Qualnet 4.0 simulation engine is used for discrete element simulation. Database interaction is implemented using Microsoft SQL Express 2005. Extensible Markup Language (XML) [5] data modeling is done in oXygen and Altova's XML Spy and NoMagic's MagicDraw and TOPCASED are used for DODAF and UML2/SysML modeling. TOPCASED and oXygen are both available as plug-ins to the Eclipse open source framework to simplify future integration with agency-specific and corporate-specific development environments and frameworks.

The CommTax database is designed to contain the data needed to interface with various network modeling and simulation (NM&S) tools, including OPNET. In this release its connectivity is limited to interfacing with Scalable Network Technology's (SNT) QualNet and with Analytical Graphics Inc. (AGI) Satellite Toolkit (STK). The former DoD Network Warfare Simulation (NETWARS) modeling capability has been incorporated into OPNET's Joint Communication Simulation System (JCSS) libraries. Once CommTax supports an OPNET NM&S engine, the JCSS models will be interchangeable with the CommTax environment. CommTax will also be able to model Joint Tactical Radio Systems (JTRS) as mobile nodes by treating each configuration separately as ordinary OSI layer implementations and then by providing switches to handle the JTRS autonomous temporal changes among configurations. In the standalone

configuration, CommTax operates in batch mode to calculate model results and doesn't handle mobility. On the other hand, CommTax does maintain the typical parameters and values in its database that are needed to support mobility. These parameters can be used to enable CommTax to calculate the model at fixed snapshots in time. As a plug-in to another NM&S modeler, CommTax will fully support that modeler's mobility.

TYPICAL BMDS COMMTAX USAGE SCENARIO

A typical MDA BMDS scenario involving two ESGs is shown in Figure 1. In the scenario, a target missile is launched from an Asian location. The ESG for the first line of defense for intercepting the target missile is an Aegis ship at sea, its radar, and its on-board interceptor missiles with booster rockets and exoatmospheric kill vehicles (EKVs). This ESG may or may not include satellite communications reachback to fire control command centers in the Continental United States (CONUS). If the target missile in this scenario gets past the first line of defense, a second ESG consisting of a

launch detection satellite, a satellite ground terminal, a sea based radar, a ground missile defense (GMD) launch facility, and a command center come into play.

The CommTax user constructs a scenario model in four GUI interfaces: the Node editor, the Network Editor, the Traffic Editor, and the Multi-Tiered Traffic (MT) Editor. Running the scenario and displaying the results is done in the fifth Analysis Window. The user initializes or chooses a predetermined fixed node site or mobile node in the Node Editor, entering the geographic location of the fixed site or initial mobile location. The user populates a system nodes table for each node in the database with instances of the communications, network, and interface components used in the various MDA ESG nodes. Components, attributes, and the ranges of allowable attribute values are entered only once into the database. Attribute values are subsequently selected from pick lists when component instances are chosen for use in an ESG node. The attribute values of each component instance are adjusted independently. The user lays out the geographical location of the nodes used in an ESG and interconnects them in the

Figure 1. Application of CommTax modeling windows to a BMDS scenario.

Network Editor. The interconnection types that are supported are wired (typically Ethernet), fiber optic, and wireless RF links. The user then populates the Traffic Editor with the data to be passed among the nodes and the characteristics of that data. The MT Editor enables the user to set-up highly realistic, multiple traffic streams that flow randomly through portions of the ESG networks and that could contribute to network congestion. Upon running a scenario, the CommTax Analysis Window reports the point-to-point data rates and latency and whether the required data rates passed between the nodes were met. The target sense to target shoot down time is also reported. GUI tools are provided to enable the user to add reporting parameters as needed.

Once the baseline E2E strings for an ESG are defined and the component databases are populated, it is easy for system engineers, program managers, or expert implementers to change attribute values using drop-down menus to run alternative scenarios. As test development components are available or as raw test results are available, higher fidelity hardware-in-the-loop (HWIL), mixed simulation can be substituted for simulation-only results. The tool can be used during the entire lifecycle, from design and development in simulation mode, through test, verification, and validation. Additional details on the CommTax editors are available in the 2008 MILCOM paper [1].

The CommTax Architecture is shown in Figure 2. As described in the MILCOM paper [1], the first implementation of CommTax provided a software bridge to build QualNet configuration files with CommTax-generated scenario, node, and component attribute data. Since then, the CommTax Program has been awarded funding to enhance the software's capabilities by including interfaces with STK. QualNet was originally chosen as CommTax's first network partner because of its relatively straightforward and consistently formatted configuration files for defining scenarios. Thus, QualNet's extensive capability to interoperate with STK will also be available to the CommTax user. The database will be used store and to communicate all configuration data from the CommTax editors to QualNet and STK, thus enabling CommTax to handle all user interfaces to the QualNet and STK applications. Furthermore, it will be possible to import data accumulated in previous runs of QualNet into the CommTax database - this will help in populating the database with existing models.

QualNet's configuration files are not data-driven, that is

Figure 2. Commtax Architecture

the node, traffic, network attributes, and other scenario information are not maintained in standard databases so that other open software cannot easily access the information. The CommTax database will be populated with all pertinent information to parallel the data needed by QualNet and STK to run models within them, enabling CommTax to control the operation of QualNet and STK. Future capabilities will include XML translation services to handle data transfers with open and proprietary modeling packages as shown at the bottom of Figure 2.

COMMTAX COMMUNICATION SYSTEM MODEL

The communications model schematic shown in Figure 3 represents the transmitter and receiver component and interface chains that are built and adjusted in a typical CommTax model. The white blocks in the model are the components in the chain while the gray blocks are the interfaces (I/F) between the components. In the CommTax tool database, the interface blocks are treated as instances of components where the component or interface is indicated as an attribute. The communication chain type, transmitter or receiver, is also selected as an attribute of a component or interface block. The various component and interface attributes are individually selectable and adjustable as shown in the fields above the white and gray blocks.

The OSI network layers of the various components are indicated below each communication chain. The physical layer (Phy - bottom, first layer) extends throughout each chain to indicate that each component and interface are physical items. The data layers (Data - second layer) indicate where typically encoded bit streams pass from the network card through the interface to the modulator/demodulator. The network layer (IP - third layer) has

Figure 4. Basic CommTax Database Model Tables.

nodes table). The ESG nodes are connected together with the ScnHNodeConnTable (scenario history node connect table) which is an indexing table that connects node A with node B, both of which are selected from the ScnHistNodesTable. The tables on the right of Figure 4 also hold data that are entered or chosen to support a scenario and/or a particular node configuration. These tables each reference the Scenario at the ScenarioHistoryTable and/or the node at the ScnHistNodesTable. The details of these connections will be worked out as the database matures.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

It is intended that the CommTax database be able to export and import data with other modeling software applications. After the CommTax database and modeling software matures, extensible stylesheet language transformations (XSLT) will be used to import and export data with the CommTax database. The XSLT translator designs will be consistent with the DoDAF 2.0 Metamodel (DM2) [6], the DoD and NATO Information Exchange Data Model (IEDM) [7], and the DOD UCore [8].

Data mediation services are defined as helping disseminating, translating, aggregating, fusing, or integrating data and associated metadata. XML Data mediation services map individual data interpretations to the standardized data elements of the reference model. Thus, mediation services can be applied using mediation schemas to navigate from the individual service interpretation to the standard and vice versa. CommTax will have RF Communication data mediation processes and tools ready to enable customers to bridge current

legacy systems or COTS/GOTS tools with many of the new modeling and simulation initiatives at different modeling and simulation organizations [9].

The MDA CommTax project will build an RF Community of Interest (COI) [10] to come to agreement on the elements and attributes for interconnecting federated communication networks.

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SISO (Simulation Interoperability Standards Organization) : <http://www.sisostds.org>

MSCO (DOD Modeling and Simulation Coordination Office) : <http://www.msco.mil/>

NMSG (NATO Modeling Simulation Group): <http://www.rta.nato.int/>

SIAA (Simulation Association of Australia) : <http://www.siaa.asn.au>

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